

Experience with Plant-Based Meat Substitutes Promotes Sustainable Diets and the Intention to Eat Less Meat

Authors: Maiken Maier^{1,2*}, Lukas P. Fesenfeld^{1,2}, Ursa Bernardic³, Fabian Bättig⁴, Fabienne Michel⁵

Current affiliations:

¹ Albert Einstein School of Public Policy; ETH Zurich; Switzerland

² Institute for Political Science and Oeschger Centre for Climate Change Research; University of Bern; Switzerland

³ Institute for Science, Technology, and Policy; ETH Zurich; Switzerland

⁴ Department of Management, Technology, and Economics (M-TEC); ETH Zurich; Switzerland

⁵ Department of Health Sciences and Technology (D-HEST), Consumer Behavior; ETH Zurich; Switzerland

*Corresponding author: Maiken Maier, maimaier@ethz.ch, Universitätsstrasse 41, 8006 Zurich, Switzerland

Abstract

Dietary shifts toward more plant-based diets in affluent populations are critical for climate change mitigation and environmental and public health protection. Plant-based meat substitutes (PBMS) offer a promising transition pathway, yet causal evidence of how real-world consumer experience shapes product evaluations and adoption, meat substitution, and food policy support remains limited. Drawing on dual-process theory, we conducted a two-wave field-embedded survey experiment with 1219 Swiss residents. Participants randomly assigned to the treatment group received multiple home-delivered PBMS products, enabling repeated, low-effort exposure. Experience with PBMS improved product evaluations across multiple dimensions and increased the intention to consume PBMS and reduce meat consumption, with stronger effects among individuals with lower prior PBMS familiarity. In a simulated online shopping task, treated participants selected a higher share of PBMS products, although aggregate meat substitution effects were limited. The effects on policy support were selective and less consistent. These findings highlight the key role and limitations of experiential learning in supporting dietary transitions.

Keywords

food consumption, consumer behavior, sustainable consumption, meat substitution, plant-based meat substitutes, field experiment

Introduction

Reducing meat consumption is widely recognized as a central strategy for mitigating climate change, limiting biodiversity loss, and improving public health, particularly in high- and upper-middle-income countries where meat consumption levels are high and contribute disproportionately to these challenges.¹⁻⁶ In response, plant-based meat alternatives have emerged as a promising pathway to more sustainable diets.⁷⁻⁹ These alternatives range from minimally processed options, such as legumes, tofu, and tempeh, to more highly processed plant-based meat substitutes (PBMS). In this study, PBMS are defined as plant-based products designed to replicate the taste, texture, and appearance of conventional meat using relatively novel food processing techniques.^{10,11} Products such as plant-based burgers, sausages, and nuggets aim to facilitate dietary change among meat eaters by offering familiar, meat-like alternatives with a lower environmental footprint.¹¹⁻¹³ Although their level of processing remains debated, recent multi-criteria assessments have suggested that, on average, PBMS continue to provide environmental, health, and nutritional advantages over animal-based products, even if these benefits are smaller than those of minimally processed plant-based foods.⁹

A growing body of research shows that the adoption of PBMS depends on consumers' product evaluations across multiple dimensions. Perceived quality—particularly taste and texture—is central, as sensory satisfaction determines whether PBMS are considered acceptable substitutes for meat.¹³⁻¹⁸ Price and convenience further influence trial and repeated consumption.^{19,20} Health perceptions and beliefs about climate, environmental, and animal welfare impacts also shape consumer acceptance.^{14,21} However, consumers often underestimate the environmental benefits of PBMS and remain skeptical about their health implications and degree of processing.^{16,21-24}

Despite rapid market growth, the extent to which PBMS consumption can meaningfully substitute for animal meat at scale remains unclear. While PBMS are gaining traction, persistent barriers—including taste concerns, perceived health risks, higher prices, and entrenched consumption habits—continue to limit widespread adoption.^{10,11,13-16,21,23,25-30} Moreover, ongoing debates question whether PBMS primarily complement rather than replace meat consumption.^{10,11,17,20,24-26,29-43} A particularly important barrier to adoption is limited real-world consumer experience with PBMS.^{13,26,37,44} Crucially, however, there remains limited causal evidence on whether repeated real-world experiences with PBMS affect product evaluations, consumption intentions, substitution patterns, and support for related food policies, especially from experimental studies with large and representative samples.^{10,26,27}

In this study, we address this gap by experimentally examining how repeated, low-effort experiences with PBMS influence consumers' product evaluations, intentions to increase PBMS consumption and to reduce meat consumption, stated purchasing decisions, and support for related food policies. By providing causal evidence on the role of experiential exposure in shaping consumer perceptions and behavioral intentions, we advance our understanding of the mechanisms underlying PBMS adoption and potential substitution effects.^{10,26,27} Importantly, our intervention goes beyond information provision by directly facilitating repeated real-world product experiences while reducing key adoption barriers, such as convenience, access, and cost. Our approach builds on the premise that PBMS must become more familiar and integrated into everyday eating routines to generate meaningful adoption and substitution effects.^{10,13,26,45} Food choices are often shaped by habits, learned preferences, and simplified decision rules, particularly in complex and time-constrained retail environments.^{13,37,44} Drawing on dual-process models of decision-making and insights from behavioral economics, we conceptualize everyday food consumption decisions as predominantly driven by intuitive, experience-based processes (System 1), whereas more deliberate and reflective evaluations (System 2) require greater cognitive effort.^{46,47} In such contexts, repeated direct product experiences can play a central role in updating beliefs and preferences when information alone may be insufficient to shift entrenched habits.

Based on this framework, we argue that repeated low-effort exposure to PBMS may shift consumers' intuitive product evaluations through experiential learning. Accordingly, we expect that in-home product experiences that consumers perceive as positive may revise perceptions of taste, quality, healthfulness, and environmental impact, thereby increasing their intentions to incorporate PBMS into everyday diets and to reduce meat consumption. As these experience-based preferences become more established and embedded in routines, they may also increasingly inform more reflective judgments about food. In line with dual-process theory, subsequent decisions that require greater deliberation, such as evaluating dietary change or forming views on related food policies, may align with these experience-based preferences through post hoc rationalization processes.⁴⁷ At the same time, research on behavioral and policy spillovers suggests mixed findings.^{10,26,48,49} While some studies have documented positive spillovers from individual pro-environmental behaviors to policy support⁴⁸, others have found null or even crowding-out effects.⁴⁸⁻⁵¹ A recent study showed that greater PBMS experience is linked to higher support for policies to reduce meat consumption by altering individuals' perceived costs and benefits of food policy change.¹⁰ Therefore, we cautiously expect that positive PBMS experiences—via experiential learning—can alter consumers' utility calculus and increase support for food policies aiming to shift demand toward more plant-based foods. In this way, experiential exposure may contribute to gradual shifts in both behavioral intentions and wider attitudes toward

dietary change and food policy.

To test these propositions, we conducted a pre-registered, field-embedded survey experiment with a representative sample of 1,219 meat-eating Swiss residents in collaboration with a leading domestic PBMS producer. After collecting baseline data on attitudes, intentions, and key predictors of food consumption behavior in a pre-treatment survey, participants were randomly assigned to a control group or to a treatment group that received home-delivered PBMS products free of charge that were sufficient for preparing approximately two to three meals. The treatment was explicitly designed to enable low-effort, real-world, repeated product experiences. A second post-treatment survey wave assessed post-treatment changes in product evaluations, behavioral intentions, stated purchasing decisions, and food policy support. We omitted vegan and vegetarian consumers and focused on meat eaters because substitution effects at scale depend on behavioral changes within this group. Prior research has indicated that individuals motivated by environmental or health concerns—such as flexitarians or those seeking to reduce meat intake—are particularly open to dietary change but often unwilling to eliminate meat entirely. These consumers tend to seek convenient and palatable plant-based alternatives that closely resemble conventional meat products.^{13,15,21,22,26,42} This segment constitutes a substantial share of the population and is especially likely to integrate PBMS as convenient meat alternatives into their diets when these products are perceived as attractive, suitable substitutes.^{13,16,21,22,26}

Main results

This section presents the overall treatment effects on the key outcome variables. In total, 1219 participants were randomly assigned to either a control group ($n = 509$), which received no products, or a treatment group ($n = 710$), which received a home-delivered shipment of PBMS products (kebabs, chicken, and/or skewers) selected by the participants themselves. The treatment products were chosen to induce a positive PBMS experience based on high average product ratings, attractiveness across different consumer segments in Switzerland, and usability in a variety of everyday recipes to facilitate convenient integration into regular cooking routines (see Methods and Appendix A). Fig.1 summarizes the treatment effects on indices capturing general PBMS evaluation criteria, including perceived quality, healthiness, price, convenience, environmental impact, and animal welfare.

Figure 1 - Experiential treatment effects on PBMS evaluation indices compared to the control group (dashed baseline). The indices capture perceived quality, health, price, convenience, environmental impact, and animal welfare. All outcomes are measured on seven-point Likert scales, with higher values indicating more positive evaluations. Error bars represent 95% (outer) and 90% (inner) confidence intervals based on OLS regressions with robust standard errors. Full regression outputs are reported in Appendix C.

Consistent with our preregistered hypotheses, treated participants generally evaluated PBMS products significantly more positively than control participants across all evaluation indices: perceived quality ($\beta = .34$ SD, 95% CI [.25, .44], $p < .001$), healthiness ($\beta = .41$ SD, 95% CI [.31, .51], $p < .001$), price ($\beta = .29$ SD, 95% CI [.18, .40], $p < .001$), convenience ($\beta = .30$ SD, 95% CI [.21, .39], $p < .001$), environmental and climate impact ($\beta = .29$

SD, 95% CI [.19, .40], $p < .001$), and animal welfare ($\beta = .16$ SD, 95% CI [.06, .26], $p < .01$). The standardized effect sizes fell in the small-to-medium range. Overall, repeated in-home PBMS exposure significantly improved general product evaluations across a broad set of purchasing criteria. As a robustness and heterogeneity check, we estimated exploratory models using binary indicators for selecting a given PBMS treatment product (kebab, chicken, or skewers), irrespective of whether it was selected alone or in combination with other products (see Appendix D1). The treatment effects remained positive across all product subgroups. Although effect magnitudes varied somewhat, no single product type accounted for the overall pattern of improved PBMS evaluations. Thus, the experiential effects were robust across product variants rather than being driven by exposure to a specific item.

Fig.2 presents the treatment effects on the intention to consume PBMS and to reduce meat consumption. In line with preregistered expectations, treated participants reported a significantly higher intention to consume PBMS over the following six months ($\beta = .14$ SD, 95% CI [.06, .22], $p < .001$) and within the following two weeks ($\beta = .12$ SD, 95% CI [.04, .21], $p < .01$). The intention to reduce meat consumption was likewise higher for both time horizons ($\beta = .12$ SD, 95% CI [.01, .23], $p < .05$). Notably, the reported meat reduction intention was substantively identical across the two timeframes, resulting in equivalent regression estimates. Although statistically significant, the effect sizes were small. Exploratory heterogeneity analyses showed broadly similar patterns across product subgroups for PBMS consumption intentions, whereas effects on meat-reduction intentions were less consistent; most notably, they were not significant in the skewers subgroup, suggesting some product experience-related heterogeneity.

Figure 2 – Experiential treatment effects on PBMS consumption and meat reduction intentions over the next six months and next two weeks compared to the control group (dashed baseline). Outcomes are measured on seven-point Likert scales. Error bars represent 95% (outer) and 90% (inner) confidence intervals based on OLS regressions with robust standard errors. Full results are reported in Appendix C.

To assess behavioral implications beyond self-reported intentions, the participants completed a food choice task embedded in a survey simulating an online supermarket environment (see the full survey in Appendix G). This design aimed to approximate key features of real-world shopping contexts, thereby moving beyond more abstract discrete choice formats.⁵² The simulated online shop displayed products from the supermarket where participants most frequently shopped. The available options included different PBMS products (including the treatment brand), tofu, and conventional meat products (chicken and beef). Products varied in price and organic labeling to create a realistic shopping context. Fig. 3 shows the estimated treatment effects of PBMS exposure on the stated choice shares for PBMS, meat, and tofu. Consistent with our preregistered hypotheses, the participants in the treatment group selected a significantly higher share of PBMS products than the control group ($\beta = .17$ SD, 95% CI [.07, .26], $p < .001$). Importantly, the treatment group selected significantly more PBMS products from the treatment brand ($\beta = .20$ SD, 95% CI [.10, .30], $p < .001$), while no significant treatment effects were observed for the alternative PBMS brand or the less processed plant-based tofu option.

This indicates that the experiential learning effects were closely linked to the specific product and brand exposure. Moreover, we found no significant differences between the treatment and control groups in the share of meat or tofu selected.

Exploratory analyses restricted to participants who selected at least one product in the simulated shopping task (see Appendix D2, Table 38) showed a similar increase in PBMS choices ($p < .001$), accompanied by a significant reduction in meat choices ($p < .05$). A more disaggregated analysis (see Appendix D2, Table 39) indicated that although both chicken and beef shares declined, these effects were not individually statistically significant, suggesting that the treatment did not selectively drive substitution away from high-emission beef in the simulated shopping context.

Figure 3 – Experiential treatment effects on expenditure shares for meat, PBMS, and tofu in the simulated supermarket task compared with the control group (dashed baseline). Error bars represent 95% (outer) and 90% (inner) confidence intervals based on OLS regressions with robust standard errors. The full results are reported in Appendix C.

Contrary to our preregistered expectations, we did not find significant overall treatment effects on broader food policy directions in Switzerland. Specifically, the treatment did not increase support for (1) expanding plant-based food production and consumption, (2) promoting PBMS, or (3) reducing overall meat consumption. These were measured as three separate survey items capturing support for or opposition to these general policy directions. Similarly, no significant effects emerged for specific policies targeting meat reduction. These included higher taxes on meat products; requiring at least half of meals served in public canteens to be meat-free; reducing government funding for the research and development of meat products; lowering agricultural subsidies for farmers producing meat and animal feed; and increasing tariffs on animal feed imports.

Fig.4 displays the treatment effects of specific policies promoting PBMS. We observed a single significant positive effect on support for lower taxes on PBMS ($\beta = .13$ SD, 95% CI [.04, .23], $p = .005$). The effect size can be categorized as small. However, no significant effects were found for other PBMS-promoting measures, including requiring at least half of public canteen meals to contain PBMS, increasing government funding for PBMS research and development, expanding agricultural subsidies for farmers producing PBMS raw materials, or reducing tariffs on PBMS raw material imports. Exploratory heterogeneity analyses suggested somewhat stronger policy support effects among participants who sampled plant-based kebabs. Overall, however, the experiential effects on policy support were smaller and less consistent than those observed for product evaluations, intentions, and stated purchasing behavior.

Figure 4 – Experiential treatment effects on support for specific policies promoting PBMS (including lower taxes on PBMS and increased public R&D funding for PBMS) relative to the control group (dashed baseline). All outcomes were measured on a seven-point Likert scale, with higher values indicating greater policy support (see Methods for details). Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals (outer) and 90% confidence intervals (inner) based on OLS regressions with robust standard errors. The full regression results are reported in Appendix C.

We further conducted exploratory interaction analyses to examine whether the treatment effects varied by prior PBMS experience, prior PBMS opinion, and prior meat consumption, all measured at baseline in survey wave I (see the regression results in Appendix D3). Fig. 5 illustrates one exemplary interaction: between treatment and prior PBMS experience on the intention to increase PBMS consumption over the following six months. The negative and statistically significant interaction ($p < .05$) indicated stronger treatment effects among participants with lower prior PBMS experience. Across outcomes, interactions between treatment and prior PBMS experience were consistently negative and statistically significant for perceived quality, perceived health, perceived convenience, animal welfare, and intentions to increase PBMS consumption and reduce meat consumption (all $p < .05$). Similarly, interactions between treatment and prior PBMS opinion were negative and significant for perceived health and convenience (both $p < .05$). In contrast, no significant interactions were observed with prior meat consumption. Taken together, these exploratory findings suggest diminishing marginal returns of experiential exposure: individuals with lower baseline familiarity or less favorable prior opinions of PBMS benefited more strongly from interventions that enable direct product experience. Importantly, no evidence of backlash effects for the product experience treatment was observed among high-meat consumers.

Figure 5 – Exploratory interaction between the treatment and prior PBMS experience on consumption intentions. The figure shows the predicted intentions to consume PBMS over the following six months as a function of the treatment group (control vs. experience treatment) and prior PBMS experience. Both prior PBMS experience and PBMS consumption intentions were measured on a seven-point Likert scale, with higher values indicating more prior experience and a stronger intention to consume PBMS. Shaded areas represent 95% confidence intervals, estimated from OLS regressions with robust standard errors. The corresponding regression results are reported in D3.

Finally, our results were robust to multiple-testing correction. Applying Benjamini–Hochberg⁵³ adjusted p-values yielded the same significance conclusions as reported in the main analysis. Manipulation checks further confirmed our intended treatment effect; that is, the treated participants were significantly more aware of the treatment brand and evaluated the product and product brand more positively than the control participants (see Appendix E1).

Discussion and implications

This study contributes to the growing literature on PBMS by providing field-experimental evidence on how repeated consumer exposure shapes product evaluations, behavioral intentions, stated purchasing decisions, and policy support. Our field-embedded survey experiment showed that repeated low-effort exposure to PBMS improved product evaluations (including the perception of product quality, healthiness, environmental impact, and animal welfare) and increased intentions to incorporate PBMS into everyday diets and to reduce meat consumption. Although the effect sizes were generally small to moderate in standardized terms, they were consistent across multiple evaluative dimensions and robust to alternative specifications. These findings support the theoretical argument rooted in dual-process models of decision-making^{46,47} that repeated experiences can shift intuitive, experience-based evaluations and related behavioral intentions.

Exploratory subgroup analyses indicated that experiential effects may have varied across specific product types but showed no consistent product-specific effects. For some outcomes, effects appeared more pronounced for certain products (e.g., plant-based kebabs), but these effects were explorative, not robust, and they require future research that randomizes a larger number of different product types. While our results are in line with prior research emphasizing the importance of perceived product quality and direct experience for food adoption,^{10,13-15,17,18,26} they also showed that no single product drove the overall treatment effects. Rather, the main pattern of improved evaluations and intentions was observable across product variants. In addition, exploratory interaction analyses suggested that experiential effects were stronger among participants with lower prior PBMS experience, pointing to potential ceiling effects among individuals already familiar with such products. In contrast, our exploratory interaction analyses showed no evidence of differential treatment effects by baseline meat consumption and no signs of backlash among high meat consumers. Future research should study this further.

Although consumers' intention to reduce meat consumption increased following PBMS exposure, these effects were small in magnitude. This aligns with previous research indicating that PBMS may contribute to meat reduction, but that substitution effects are often modest.^{13,27,31} Consistent with this interpretation, exposure to PBMS did not produce statistically significant reductions in meat choice shares in the simulated online shopping environment. This finding echoes earlier studies suggesting that PBMS may complement rather than fully replace meat in many consumers' diets^{13,25,27} and highlights the need for longitudinal field experiments with revealed purchase data to assess longer-term substitution dynamics in real-world shopping contexts.

Furthermore, while we observed positive effects on PBMS product evaluations and consumption intentions, the effects on policy support were more limited and selective. We did not detect significant shifts in support for broader food policy changes or for regulatory and disincentive-based measures targeting meat reduction. Instead, experiential exposure increased support only for a specific incentive-based policy, i.e., lower taxes on PBMS, and even this effect was small in magnitude. Exploratory analyses suggested somewhat stronger policy effects among participants exposed to particular product types; however, these findings should be interpreted cautiously. Overall, experiential learning appeared to translate more readily into product-related evaluations and personal behavioral intentions than into broader food policy preferences. This contrasts with prior experimental evidence from other country contexts showing positive spillovers of PBMS experiences on food policy support.¹⁰ This divergence suggests that experiential effects on policy preferences may depend on contextual factors such as product characteristics, additional information provided, market maturity, baseline consumer attitudes, or national policy environments. Comparative experimental research across products and countries would help clarify the scope conditions under which experiential learning translates into broader policy support.

The comparatively weaker and less consistent effects on policy support also raise broader questions about the conditions under which experiential learning may spill over into deeper attitudinal change. Dual-process models suggest that while repeated experience can reshape intuitive (System 1) evaluations, more durable shifts in underlying beliefs and policy preferences may require more reflective (System 2) processing.⁵⁴ Our findings provide clear evidence for experiential shifts in product-related evaluations but offer only limited support for downstream changes in broader policy preferences. Future research should therefore examine more directly the mechanisms linking experiential learning to reflective judgment, including whether longer exposure periods or combinations of experiential and informational interventions more strongly activate deliberative processes.

This study provides initial experimental evidence that low-effort real-world exposure can serve as an entry point for shifting product evaluations and increasing PBMS uptake. However, accelerating durable dietary transitions likely requires sustained improvements in product quality, repeated positive experiences, and supportive structural and policy changes. Overall, our findings underscore the importance of experiential learning as a scalable and behaviorally grounded lever for promoting more sustainable diets while also highlighting the limits of simple low-effort exposure for generating broader attitudinal and policy change.

Methods

The aim of this pre-registered study (<https://doi.org/10.1257/rct.13528-1.0>) was to examine the extent to which experiential treatment with PBMS influences individuals' (1) evaluation of PBMS, (2) intention to reduce meat consumption, (3) intention to increase PBMS consumption, (4) stated purchasing preferences, and (5) support for food policy measures. To examine this, we conducted a field experiment embedded in two survey waves with a large sample of 1219 respondents from the German- and French-speaking regions of Switzerland. The study was fielded between May and July 2024. As part of the experimental design shown in Figure 6, respondents in the first survey wave were randomly assigned to either a control group, which received no PBMS products, or a treatment group, which received deliveries of PBMS products from a well-known Swiss brand to try at home. The package, delivered after completion of the first survey, contained enough products for approximately 2-3 meals that were intended to be prepared and consumed at home. Prior to the experimental part of this study, participants responded to a series of questions designed to measure relevant control variables in the first survey wave and dependent variables in the second survey wave.

Figure 6 – Research design.

Survey sample

Prior to data collection, approval for the study was obtained from the ETH Ethics Board (EK-2024-N-85). Study participants were recruited through a survey sample provided by the Swiss Federal Statistical Office in cooperation with the ETH Decision Science Laboratory. The sample was stratified by language region, degree of urbanization, and gender. This stratified random population sampling approach offers very high survey quality and representativeness. The respondents were informed that they were participating in a *study on innovations in energy and agriculture*. Participation was voluntary and not compensated for; however, respondents could enter a lottery for the chance to win a prize (the first prize was an iPad). For the second survey wave, the participants from the first wave were recontacted. Individuals who indicated that they did not eat meat were excluded from participating in the experiment, as the study focused on the potential of PBMS experiences to accelerate a shift toward more plant-based diets among the majority of meat eaters. In addition, individuals who did not provide informed consent for participation in the treatment were excluded. The final sample consisted of 1219 individuals who completed both survey waves and participated in the field experiment. More details on the eligibility criteria for participation are provided in Appendix A. To assess representativeness with respect to age, gender, and language region, we performed Welch's two-sample *t*-test and two chi-square tests comparing our sample to the target population. The demographic and structural composition of the sample corresponded quite closely to the Swiss residential population in the German- and French-speaking parts of Switzerland. A comparison of the sample and population statistics is presented in Appendix B.

Survey procedure and measures

The two surveys were designed and administered using Qualtrics, an online survey software platform. Participants could choose to complete the survey in German, French, or English. Following the screening process and initial demographic questions in the first survey wave, data were collected on a set of relevant control variables, as shown in Table 1. These variables were selected based on the existing literature on food consumption, which identifies them as key predictors of meat and PBMS consumption intentions, perceptions, and support for related food policy measures.

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
Age	Respondent age in years
Gender	Respondent gender (binary variable with factors Male and Female)*
Education	Respondent level of education (five-point scale from no/obligatory school to university)
Diet	Respondent diet (variable indicating whether respondents are omnivores or eat meat only (no fish); respondents who did not eat meat were excluded from the experiment)
Political orientation	Self-placement on the political spectrum (10-point Likert scale from left to right)
Urbanization level	Degree of urbanization based on place of residence (urban, suburban, rural)
Meat consumption	Meat consumption frequency prior to the treatment (seven-point Likert scale from rarely to several times a day)
Substitute consumption	PBMS consumption frequency prior to the treatment (seven-point Likert scale from never to every day)
Substitute opinion	General opinion on PBMS prior to the treatment (seven-point Likert scale from very negative to very positive)
Planted brand awareness	Awareness of the Swiss PBMS brand Planted (1 = “Yes, I know the brand and have tasted the products,” 2 = “Yes, I know the brand but have never tried the products,” and 3 = “No, I don’t know the brand”)

*Table 1 – Overview of control variables included in the analysis. *Gender was measured with the categories female, male, and non-binary/other, see Questionnaire in Appendix G. A small number of respondents identified as non-binary/other (n = 3). Due to the limited sample size and to ensure statistical robustness and anonymity, these cases were excluded from the main analyses.*

Subsequently, respondents were randomly assigned to either the control group (no experiential treatment) or the treatment group during the first survey wave. Participants in the treatment group were presented with three PBMS products (kebabs, chicken, and skewers), from which they could select their preferred options. Specific products were not randomly assigned within the treatment group; therefore, the study design did not allow for causal evaluation of product-specific experience effects. However, we opted for this approach to enhance external validity, as allowing participants to choose increased the likelihood that they would select products suited to their everyday cooking practices and personal preferences. In addition, treatment group participants were asked to select two, four, or six packages, depending on their household size, ensuring that the quantity provided was sufficient for approximately 2–3 servings per household. The treatment survey block was introduced with the following text: “We will now randomly select about half of all participants to take part in a free tasting of PBMS products from the Swiss brand Planted. If you are randomly selected, you will receive a free selection of PBMS products from the brand Planted, delivered to your home at the time of your choice.” Fig. 7 displays the product selection screen shown to participants prior to making their choice.

Planted Product Selection

Figure 7 – Product selection survey item displayed to participants while making their product choice.

The PBMS manufacturer was responsible for administering the treatment delivery after receiving the delivery addresses of the experiment participants who provided informed consent, as well as their preferred delivery dates. All product deliveries took place between June 4 and June 14, 2024 (excluding weekends and Mondays). Finally, in the second post-treatment survey wave, data were collected on the relevant dependent variables. These included measures capturing participants' evaluations of PBMS, intentions to reduce meat consumption and to increase PBMS consumption, stated purchasing preferences, and support for food policy measures, as follows:

- DV1a–f: PBMS evaluation indices (seven-point Likert scale ranging from “very negative” to “very positive”): quality, healthiness, convenience, environmental and climate impact, animal welfare, and price.
- DV2a and b: Intentions to purchase PBMS in the future and in the following two weeks (seven-point Likert scale ranging from “very unlikely” to “very likely”).
- DV3a and b: Intentions to reduce meat consumption in the future and in the following two weeks (seven-point Likert scale ranging from “very unlikely” to “very likely”).
- DV4a–c: Stated preferences in a hypothetical choice task designed to resemble the retailer’s online shop environment. Participants indicated how many units of each product they wished to purchase. Shares were then calculated as continuous outcomes, representing the proportion of the participants’ chosen baskets allocated to each product category: meat, PBMS, and tofu.
- DV5a–c: General food policy support (seven-point Likert scale from fully reject to fully support) on policies in Switzerland to expand the production and consumption of plant-based foods, promote PBMS, and reduce meat consumption
- DV6a–e: Specific food policy support (seven-point Likert scale ranging from “fully reject” to “fully support”) on policies in Switzerland aiming to promote PBMS, including lower taxes on PBMS, at least half of the meals in public canteens containing PBMS, increased government funding for research and development of PBMS, increased agricultural subsidies for farmers producing PBMS raw materials, and reduced tariffs on PBMS raw material imports.
- DV7a–e: Specific food policy support (seven-point Likert scale ranging from “fully reject” to “fully support”) on policies in Switzerland aiming to reduce meat consumption, including higher taxes on meat, at least half of the meals in public canteens being meat-free, reduced government funding on the research and development of meat products, reduced agricultural subsidies for farmers producing meat and animal feed, and increased tariffs on animal feed imports.

More details on the variables can be found in Appendix B, the full survey questionnaire is in Appendix G.

Data analysis

Balance checks confirmed that the randomization of the treatment was successful. The treatment and control groups did not differ significantly in terms of standard sociodemographic, economic, or diet-related variables (see Appendix F). For the main analysis, the regression model below, with robust standard errors, was calculated for each dependent variable (see Appendix C1):

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \mathbf{group}_i + \mathbf{X}'_i \boldsymbol{\beta} + \varepsilon_i \quad (1),$$

where Y_i is the dependent variable, \mathbf{group}_i is a binary variable indicating treatment assignment (1 = treatment, 0 = control), and \mathbf{X}_i is a vector of individual-level control variables. In addition, individual characteristics known to influence PBMS evaluations, food consumption behavior, and policy support were included as control variables to improve the precision and robustness of the estimated treatment effects. These included age, gender, education, and general opinion of PBMS. More details on the explanatory and control variables are provided in Appendix B. To facilitate interpretation and comparability across outcomes, we also estimated models with standardized dependent variables and reported standardized treatment effects (in standard deviation units; also see Appendix C2). To account for multiple hypothesis testing across outcome domains, p-values were adjusted using the Benjamini & Hochberg⁵³ procedure to control for the false discovery rate. Finally, we conducted a set of exploratory analyses (see Appendix D), including interaction models examining heterogeneity by prior PBMS experiences, prior PBMS attitudes, and baseline meat consumption, as well as product-specific subgroup analyses and additional robustness checks.

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Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests related to this study. The research forms part of a broader long-term project conducted in collaboration with a leading Swiss PBMS producer and with two major Swiss retailers. Importantly, funding for the project is independent and not provided by the collaboration partners (see funding sources above). While the partners will receive access to the aggregated and anonymized results of the independent scientific analyses, they had no influence on the study design, data analysis, or reporting.

Data and code availability statement

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study as well as the R code used to analyze the data and relevant study documentation are published in the Harvard Dataverse public repository: Maier, Maiken; Fesenfeld, Lukas Paul; Bernardic, Ursa; Michel, Fabienne; Bättig, Fabian, 2026, "Replication Data for "Experience with Plant-Based Meat Substitutes Promotes Sustainable Diets and the Intention to Eat Less Meat"", <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/POONP7>, Harvard Dataverse, V1

Contributions

M.M.: Conceptualization; Methodology; Investigation; Data curation; Formal analysis; Writing – original draft; Writing – review and editing. L.F.: Funding acquisition; Conceptualization; Methodology; Investigation; Writing – original draft; Writing – review and editing. U.B.: Conceptualization; Data curation; Formal analysis; Writing - review and editing. F.B.: Conceptualization; Data curation; Formal analysis; F.M.: Conceptualization; Writing – review and editing.

Corresponding author

Correspondence to Maiken Maier, maimaier@ethz.ch

References

1. Clark, M. A. *et al.* Global food system emissions could preclude achieving the 1.5° and 2°C climate change targets. *Science* **370**, 705–708 (2020).
2. Godfray, H. C. J. *et al.* Meat consumption, health, and the environment. *Science* **361**, (2018).
3. Poore, J. & Nemecek, T. Reducing food’s environmental impacts through producers and consumers. *Science* **360**, 987–992 (2018).
4. Springmann, M., Godfray, H. C. J., Rayner, M. & Scarborough, P. Analysis and valuation of the health and climate change cobenefits of dietary change. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **113**, 4146–4151 (2016).
5. Springmann, M. & Freund, F. Options for reforming agricultural subsidies from health, climate, and economic perspectives. *Nat. Commun.* **13**, 82 (2022).
6. Willett, W. *et al.* Food in the Anthropocene: the EAT–Lancet Commission on healthy diets from sustainable food systems. *The Lancet* **393**, 447–492 (2019).
7. Auclair, O., Eustachio Colombo, P., Milner, J. & Burgos, S. A. Partial substitutions of animal with plant protein foods in Canadian diets have synergies and trade-offs among nutrition, health and climate outcomes. *Nat. Food* **5**, 148–157 (2024).
8. Grummon, A. H., Lee, C. J. Y., Robinson, T. N., Rimm, E. B. & Rose, D. Simple dietary substitutions can reduce carbon footprints and improve dietary quality across diverse segments of the US population. *Nat. Food* **4**, 966–977 (2023).
9. Springmann, M. A multicriteria analysis of meat and milk alternatives from nutritional, health, environmental, and cost perspectives. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **121**, e2319010121 (2024).
10. Fesenfeld, L. *et al.* How information, social norms, and experience with novel meat substitutes can create positive political feedback and demand-side policy change. *Food Policy* **117**, 102445 (2023).
11. Jahn, S., Guhl, D. & Erhard, A. Substitution patterns and price response for plant-based meat alternatives. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **121**, e2319016121 (2024).
12. Qaim, M., Barrangou, R. & Ronald, P. C. Sustainability of animal-sourced foods and plant-based alternatives. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **121**, e2400495121 (2024).
13. Siegrist, M. & Hartmann, C. Consumer acceptance of novel food technologies. *Nat. Food* **1**, 343–350 (2020).
14. Onwezen, M. C., Bouwman, E. P., Reinders, M. J. & Dagevos, H. A systematic review on consumer acceptance of alternative proteins: Pulses, algae, insects, plant-based meat alternatives, and cultured meat. *Appetite* **159**, 105058 (2021).
15. Michel, F., Hartmann, C. & Siegrist, M. Consumers’ associations, perceptions and acceptance of meat and plant-based meat alternatives. *Food Qual. Prefer.* **87**, 104063 (2021).
16. Michel, F., Knaapila, A., Hartmann, C. & Siegrist, M. A multi-national comparison of meat eaters’ attitudes and expectations for burgers containing beef, pea or algae protein. *Food Qual. Prefer.* **91**, 104195 (2021).
17. Siddiqui, S. A. *et al.* Consumer Acceptance of Alternative Proteins: A Systematic Review of Current Alternative Protein Sources and Interventions Adapted to Increase Their Acceptability. *Sustainability* **14**, 15370 (2022).
18. Fehér, A., Gazdecki, M., Véha, M., Szakály, M. & Szakály, Z. A Comprehensive Review of the Benefits of and the Barriers to the Switch to a Plant-Based Diet. *Sustainability* **12**, 4136 (2020).
19. Harguess, J. M., Crespo, N. C. & Hong, M. Y. Strategies to reduce meat consumption: A systematic literature review of experimental studies. *Appetite* **144**, 104478 (2020).
20. Nguyen, J., Ferraro, C., Sands, S. & Luxton, S. Alternative protein consumption: A systematic review and future research directions. *Int. J. Consum. Stud.* **46**, 1691–1717 (2022).
21. Hartmann, C., Furtwaengler, P. & Siegrist, M. Consumers’ evaluation of the environmental friendliness, healthiness and naturalness of meat, meat substitutes, and other protein-rich foods. *Food Qual. Prefer.* **97**, 104486 (2022).
22. Hartmann, C. & Siegrist, M. Consumer perception and behaviour regarding sustainable protein consumption: A systematic review. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* **61**, 11–25 (2017).
23. Siegrist, M. & Hartmann, C. Impact of sustainability perception on consumption of organic meat and meat substitutes. *Appetite* **132**, 196–202 (2019).
24. Taylor, H., Tonsor, G. T., Lusk, J. L. & Schroeder, T. C. Benchmarking US consumption and perceptions of beef and PL ant- BASED proteins. *Appl. Econ. Perspect. Policy* aapp.13287 (2022) doi:10.1002/aapp.13287.
25. Cuffey, J., Chenarides, L., Li, W. & Zhao, S. Consumer spending patterns for plant-based meat alternatives. *Appl. Econ. Perspect. Policy* **45**, 63–85 (2023).
26. Fesenfeld, L. P. *et al.* Tasting and labeling meat substitute products can affect consumers’ product evaluations and preferences. *Food Qual. Prefer.* **118**, 105184 (2024).

27. Siegrist, M., Michel, F. & Hartmann, C. The shift from meat to plant-based proteins: consumers and public policy. *Curr. Opin. Food Sci.* **58**, 101182 (2024).
28. Fischer, A. R. H., Onwezen, M. C. & Van Der Meer, M. Consumer perceptions of different protein alternatives. in *Meat and Meat Replacements* 333–362 (Elsevier, 2023). doi:10.1016/B978-0-323-85838-0.00005-5.
29. Safdar, B. *et al.* Prospects for Plant-Based Meat: Current Standing, Consumer Perceptions, and Shifting Trends. *Foods* **11**, 3770 (2022).
30. Slade, P. If you build it, will they eat it? Consumer preferences for plant-based and cultured meat burgers. *Appetite* **125**, 428–437 (2018).
31. Apostolidis, C. & McLeay, F. Should we stop meating like this? Reducing meat consumption through substitution. *Food Policy* **65**, 74–89 (2016).
32. Bianchi, F. *et al.* Replacing meat with alternative plant-based products (RE-MAP): a randomized controlled trial of a multicomponent behavioral intervention to reduce meat consumption. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* **115**, 1357–1366 (2022).
33. Carlsson, F., Kataria, M. & Lampi, E. How much does it take? Willingness to switch to meat substitutes. *Ecol. Econ.* **193**, 107329 (2022).
34. Hoek, A. C. *et al.* Replacement of meat by meat substitutes. A survey on person- and product-related factors in consumer acceptance. *Appetite* **56**, 662–673 (2011).
35. Hoek, A. C. *et al.* Are meat substitutes liked better over time? A repeated in-home use test with meat substitutes or meat in meals. *Food Qual. Prefer.* **28**, 253–263 (2013).
36. Neuhofer, Z. T. & Lusk, J. L. Most plant-based meat alternative buyers also buy meat: an analysis of household demographics, habit formation, and buying behavior among meat alternative buyers. *Sci. Rep.* **12**, 13062 (2022).
37. Schösler, H., Boer, J. de & Boersema, J. J. Can we cut out the meat of the dish? Constructing consumer-oriented pathways towards meat substitution. *Appetite* **58**, 39–47 (2012).
38. Siegrist, M. & Hartmann, C. Why alternative proteins will not disrupt the meat industry. *Meat Sci.* **203**, 109223 (2023).
39. Taufik, D., Verain, M. C. D., Bouwman, E. P. & Reinders, M. J. Determinants of real-life behavioural interventions to stimulate more plant-based and less animal-based diets: A systematic review. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* **93**, 281–303 (2019).
40. Zhao, S., Wang, L., Hu, W. & Zheng, Y. Meet the meatless: Demand for new generation plant-based meat alternatives. *Appl. Econ. Perspect. Policy* aapp.13232 (2022) doi:10.1002/aapp.13232.
41. MacDonald, J., Brauer, P. & Yi, S. Meat reduction among post-secondary students: Exploration of motives, barriers, diets and preferences for meals with partial and full meat substitution. *Appetite* **188**, 106977 (2023).
42. Petersen, T., Denker, T.-L., Koppenberg, M. & Hirsch, S. Revealed preferences on meat substitute consumption and political attitudes - Testing the left-right and environmental concerns framework. *Appetite* **199**, 107371 (2024).
43. White, S. K., Ballantine, P. W. & Ozanne, L. K. Consumer adoption of plant-based meat substitutes: A network of social practices. *Appetite* **175**, 106037 (2022).
44. Happer, C. & Wellesley, L. Meat consumption, behaviour and the media environment: a focus group analysis across four countries. *Food Secur.* **11**, 123–139 (2019).
45. Szenderák, J., Fróna, D. & Rákos, M. Consumer Acceptance of Plant-Based Meat Substitutes: A Narrative Review. *Foods* **11**, 1274 (2022).
46. Chaiken, S. & Trope, Y. *Dual-Process Theories in Social Psychology*. (The Guilford Press, 1999).
47. Kahneman, D. *Thinking, Fast and Slow*. (Farrar, Straus and Giroux, New York, 2011).
48. Thøgersen, J., Vatn, A. & Aasen, M. The chicken or the egg? Spillover between private climate action and climate policy support. *J. Environ. Psychol.* **99**, 102434 (2024).
49. Ling, M., Liu, C., Xu, L. & Yang, H. Carrot and stick incentive policies for climate change mitigation: A survey experiment on crowding out of public support. *Ecol. Econ.* **223**, 108242 (2024).
50. Knook, J., Dorner, Z. & Stahlmann-Brown, P. Priming for individual energy efficiency action crowds out support for national climate change policy. *Ecol. Econ.* **191**, 107239 (2022).
51. Ling, M. & Xu, L. Incentivizing household recycling crowds out public support for other waste management policies: A long-term quasi-experimental study. *J. Environ. Manage.* **299**, 113675 (2021).
52. Simonetti, A., Mehlhose, C., Klink-Lehmann, J. & Lemken, D. Supermarket Settings and Consumer Behavior: A Systematic Mapping Review and Future Research Avenues. *Int. J. Consum. Stud.* **50**, e70196 (2026).
53. Benjamini, Y. & Hochberg, Y. Controlling the False Discovery Rate: A Practical and Powerful Approach to Multiple Testing. *J. R. Stat. Soc. Ser. B Methodol.* **57**, 289–300 (1995).

54. Van Loo, E. J., Hoefkens, C. & Verbeke, W. Healthy, sustainable and plant-based eating: Perceived (mis)match and involvement-based consumer segments as targets for future policy. *Food Policy* **69**, 46–57 (2017).